

IMPROVED LEADERSHIP TRAITS EXPRESSION SYSTEM FOR PRIVATE INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION EFFECTIVENESS

Dr. Michael Martinson Boakye

Lecturer of the J. S. Addo School of Business, Marshalls University College, Ghana

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Abstract:

An improved leadership traits expression system influences private institution of higher education. This contemporary study identifies three major components of leadership traits expression system to consist leadership style, Leadership skills and Leadership capabilities with Leadership competency having mediating role. This paper used the Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling using the Smart PLS3 software to synthesise an improved leadership traits expression system. Again, extensive literature review, which included scholarly articles, books, and relevant publications as well as interviews were conducted with leaders from successful private institutions to gain further insights into their experiences and practices. The study also found out that suitable leadership traits expression model that is effective to give optimal results to private institutions of higher education should have component of transformational, authoritative leadership styles with three major leadership skills (organisational strategy, college advocacy and professionalism) along with leadership capabilities (intelligence, personality and learning and motivation) combining to influence the leaders competency in order to result in organisational effectiveness of private institutions of higher education. The leader's skills and capability contribute to the overall competency of the leader in the quest to achieve organisational effectiveness. It is therefore recommended that Private Institution of Higher Education develop capacity to improve upon the three component of Leadership traits expression.

Key Words: Leadership Traits Expression, Higher Education Effectiveness, Private Institutions of Higher Education

Introduction:

Private institutions operate differently under certain circumstances as compared to public institutions. Therefore, it requires leaders who possess the necessary skills and traits to navigate through challenges and drive organizational agility and success. This paper aims to identify and explore key leadership traits expression that contributes to the success of private institutions of higher education, as well as propose an improved system for expressing these traits to enhance organizational effectiveness in private institutions of higher education. This research paper highlights the significance of leadership traits expression in private institutions of higher education. By implementing the improved leadership traits expression model, private institutions can enhance leadership effectiveness and surmount challenges in order to ultimately achieve organizational success. This research contributes to the existing literature on leadership in higher education and provides workable recommendations for private institutions to do well in an increasingly competitive educational landscape.

Literature Review:

There is a plethora of studies concerning effectiveness of educational institutions and the factors affecting effectiveness, however, the actual interpretation and use of the knowledge is limited because practitioners have not translated the findings of the studies into organisationally based action because of the differences in the institutional operations, size and vision. A lot of indicators similar in nature have been adopted as a model for organisational effectiveness in privately owned colleges and universities. Some studies on models for organisational effectiveness in colleges and universities are as follows:

Antia and Cuthbert (1976) organized a study on the success factors of polytechnics and in qualitative model suggested nine critical factors that determined the effectiveness of educational institutions. They indicated that these success factors are closely related to each other and therefore the neglect of one affects the other in the long term. The identified variables are: Social tune, Cost effectiveness, Course development, Cooperate reputation, Investment in human capital, Physical facilities development, Student relations, Quality of employee relations and Public responsibility.

Ashraf and Kadir (2012) assert that it is necessary to spot and comparatively emphasized by all institutions because the achievement of success in the nine areas is key to growth and effectiveness. Institutions must be socially tuned by mounting courses and programmes that meet the demands of industry. However, that must be done considering cost effectiveness in all of the institution's activities. Once the business environment is exacerbated by several changes, institutions must constantly develop new courses and invest in human capital

to give them the needed expertise to hand new courses whiles developing physical facilities to help the cogent delivery of new programme. Educational institutions must be interested in enhancing good student's relations and quality employee relations in order to allow for tranquility in the institution's environment with the sense of corporate reputation and responsibility towards the public. Any educational institution that is able to handle or satisfy all these constituencies is rated effective.

Cameron (1978) in his study proposed organisational effectiveness model for 4 year colleges using 57 item questionnaires which were perception based on the effectiveness of institutions. He came up with nine indicators that influence institutional effectiveness: student educational satisfaction, student academic development, student career development, student personal development, faculty and administrator employment satisfaction, professional development and quality of faculty, system openness and community interaction, resource acquisition and organisation health. According to Cameron (1978) the above constituencies are vital for any institution's survival and agility. Ashraf and Kadir (2012) add that base on Cameron's models, it is important for all contextual factors to be considered before organisational effectiveness criteria is selected. To compare other models of effectiveness in higher education to that of Cameron, there is no much deviation. Most identified criteria or factors are similar and geared towards the same purpose. However, the application of any of these models to any educational institution may depend on myriad situational variables like demography, economics, government policy, technology among others.

Kleeman and Richardson (1985) in a study on student characteristics and perception of university effectiveness in three public universities in Arizona, identify 10 factors that determine effectiveness of education institutions: Programmes and service for students, Attention to women and minorities, Quality of teaching and research, Publication of knowledge and research, Workshops and Counseling to broaden access, Sports, Focus on cultural activities, Programme for graduates, Leasing facilities and Enhancement of standards.

The proper consideration of the ten determinants in decision making was seen as factors that yielded institutional effectiveness. Though the model proposed by Kleeman and Richardson (1985) looks very different and comprehensive to that of Antia and Cuthbert (1976) some of the success factors may be interrelated or yield similar outcomes. The study of Kleeman and Richardson (1985) concluded that among the ten factors stipulated, quality of teaching and research and programmes for graduates are most necessary to respondents and therefore must be given all the attention it desires.

Pounder (1999) in a study on "organisational effectiveness in higher education" in Hong Kong educational institutions established nine factors that influence the effectiveness of institutions. The study was done in 7 institutions with administration and academic staff as study group. The nine factors included: productivity efficiency, quality, cohesion, adaptability readiness, information management - communication, growth, planning - goal setting, human resource development and stability control. The study concludes that among the nine factors in the model, planning and productivity triggered the effective performance of universities in Hong Kong. A firm grip on these areas better the chances of institutional survival. An, Yom & Ruggiero (2011) studied into how organisational culture and quality of work life influence organisational effectiveness in Korean University hospitals. Their study evaluates organisations effectiveness at two levels: Job satisfaction and Organisational involvement. In the study, the factors that promoted organisational effectiveness were: quality of career, good organisational culture and care (Salanke, 2014).

Salanke also studied into organisational effectiveness in higher education of Polytechnics in Nigeria. Salanke (2014) used three models to assess the effectiveness of the university with different indicators. The Human relations model had the following indicators: Staff training and development, Remuneration and campus relationship. The open system model had the following indicators: Acquisition of resources, Physical infrastructure and equipment's and Accreditation. The rational goal model has only one indicator: strategic planning. Internal Process model has the following indicators: accountability, internal resources allocation and information communication technology. Through the application of different models, Solanke (2014) highlight ten factors that influence higher education in Nigeria. The ability of any institution to respond adequately to these evaluated criteria assumes institutional progress and agility. The criteria include staff remuneration, campus relationship, resource acquisition, physical infrastructures and equipment, accreditation, strategic planning, accountability, internal resource allocation and information communication technology

In the study Salanke (2014 p. 230) concludes that "quality represents the fulfillment of obligation by institutions to serve societies well by producing well rounded professionals. Despite all these studies into organisational effectiveness (Solanke, 2014; An et al 2011, Ponder, 1999, Kleeman, 1985, Antia, 1976) researchers are more appease with the study of Cameron (1978) on the evaluation of organisational effectiveness in higher education as indicated by other researchers (Gigliotti, 1987; Hertelendy, 2010; Kwan & Walker, 2003; Lejeune & Vas 2009; Smart, 2003; Vinitwatanakhun, 1998).

Empirical Results and Analysis:

Drawing from the knowledge from the output of the structural equation modeling and existing literature, leadership traits expression model has three major components and one other component serving as mediating variable:

- Leadership Styles
- Leadership Skills
- Leadership Capabilities
- Leadership Competency (Mediator)

The key elements of all the leadership traits expression components are as follows: Leadership style; transactional style, transformational style, authoritarian style and laissez faire style. Leadership skills; organisational strategy, college advocacy and professionalism. Leadership capabilities: intelligence, personality and learning & motivation. Leadership competency (mediation variable); knowledge and experience.

Structural path	Path coefficient	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Capability -> organisational effectiveness	0.206	1.982	0.035
Skills -> organisational effectiveness	0.582	8.563	0.000
Style -> organisational effectiveness	0.042	3.458	0.027

Figure 1: Path coefficient of leadership traits expression and organizational effectiveness

Socio- economic political factors of the system; drawing from the findings of this study and knowledge from existing literature, the following factors determine Leadership traits expression system within an organisation: Leaders personality, organisational culture, workforce diversity, external business environment, organisational vision and organisational structure.

Drawing from knowledge from existing literature, specifications for of Leadership traits expression system are identified. To use this leadership traits expression system effectively the following are required within an organisational context: communication, discipline, commitment, flexibility, corporation and collaboration and positional power. The rest include organisational structure, teamwork, adaptability, studiousness, need for achievement, teachability, dutifulness and motivation. Procedures of the leadership traits expression system includes: Establishment of leadership trait expression system policy; approval of the system policy; provision of training and retraining on the leadership trait expression system policy; implementation of the system and monitoring and evaluation of leadership traits expression system.

Using the Leadership traits expression system in private institutions of higher education will bring a change and results in the following: Leadership styles will result in 4.2% of the overall effectiveness of private institutions of higher education. Leadership skills will result in 58.2% effectiveness of private institutions of higher education and leadership capabilities will also result 20.6% in the total effectiveness of private institutions of higher education. Leadership styles, leadership skills and leadership capabilities contributing to the total leadership competency will results in 38.3% of organisational effectiveness in private institutions of Higher Education.

Summary of the Synthesised System:

Figure 2: Boakye's Leadership traits expression system for organisational effectiveness in PIHE

Source: Researcher's construct (2022).

Note: Tr = Transformational Leadership, Tn = Transactional Leadership, Auth = Authoritative Leadership, Lfl = Laissez faire; Intel = Intelligence, Pes = Personality, L&M = Learning & Motivation, OS = Org Strategy, CA = College Advocacy, Prof = Professionalism, Kn = Knowledge, Exp = Experience, OEQTR = Quality teaching and research, OERE = Resources, OEEO = University outlook

Figure 2 identifies and summarizes the components of an improved and functional leadership traits expression system that gives optimal private institutions of higher education effectiveness. University administrators and leaders must acquire these characteristics such as contained in this model so as to promote effectiveness in tertiary institutions because it is helpful to outperform competitors and finally gain organisational agility and sustainability.

Summary and Conclusions:

The study found out that suitable leadership traits expression model that is effective to give optimal results to private institutions of higher education should have component of transformational, authoritative leadership styles with three major leadership skills (organisational strategy, college advocacy and professionalism) along with leadership capabilities (intelligence, personality and learning and motivation) combining to influence the leaders competency in order to result in organisational effectiveness of private institutions of higher education. The leader's skills and capabilities contribute to the overall competency of the leader in the quest to achieve organisational effectiveness.

Leadership models provide a template on how to achieve optimal leadership results in private institutions of higher education. Transformational, transactional, authoritarian and laissez-faire leadership styles complement each other in achieving organisational success though transformational leadership plays a dominant role. It is therefore important for university leadership in private institutions of higher education to understand the various strengths and weaknesses of leadership styles and how to use it in the organisational context to achieve leadership purpose.

Leadership skills and leadership capabilities are essential components that determine leadership success in private institutions of higher education. Synthesizing leadership system for an enhanced and optimal effectiveness in PIHE, the component should include leadership styles (transformational, authoritative); leadership skills (organisational strategy, college advocacy and professionalism) and leadership capabilities (intelligence, personality and learning and motivation) for which leadership competency plays a mediation role in leading to organisational effectiveness.

The study identifies leadership skills, leadership styles and leadership capabilities as components of Leadership traits expression model with mediation of leadership competency leading to organisational effectiveness. It is therefore recommended that effective and efficient Leadership traits expression model for private tertiary education must pay keen attention to the two dimensions of leadership styles (transformational and authoritative); the three skills set (organisational strategy, college advocacy and professionalism) and leadership capabilities (intelligence, personality and learning and motivation) in order to leverage them for optimal organisational effectiveness.

This means that policy makers and shareholders of higher institutions must invest in training university administrators in order to equip them for better understanding and utilization of all the three components of the Leadership traits expression (leadership styles, leadership skills and leadership capabilities). When the training programmes are done properly, the effectiveness agenda and business strategy of the university will be achieved.

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